

QUESTIONS ABOUT ORGANIZING INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY AT THE INDUSTRIAL PLANTS

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Abstract: In this article were studied questions regarding organizing innovative activity at the enterprises. Discussed the changes necessary for organizing innovative activity at the plants and explained their essence of them. Besides, were developed recommendations regarding learning and valuing the results of the innovative activity.

Keywords: competition, innovation, human resource, organization structure, competitive advantage, strategy, innovation's efficiency.

Introduction. Nowadays, the development of innovative potential in advanced economy countries and achieving competitive advantage had become the main criterion for ensuring the sustainable growth of national economies. Especially, since the 80s of the 20th century, the production of products with high scientific capacity had increased and in the present day, it has a large share in world trade. Taking into account this situation, the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan has defined the development of innovative potential as a priority direction of economic development. In particular, the adoption of documents such as the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 (PF-4947, 2017), as well as the «Year of Support for Active Entrepreneurship, Innovative Ideas and Technologies» and the State Law «On Innovative Activities» and its approval means that building a competitive economy at the international level is considered the most important task of the economic policy. In the recently announced «Global innovativeness 2022» index, the Republic of Uzbekistan took 82nd place with a score of 25.3, 3rd place after India and Iran in the group of countries of the Central and South Asian region, and 10th place in the group of «Countries with lower than average income» according to the income category (Saumitra Dutta, Bruno Lanvin, Lorena Rivera Leon, Sacha Wunsch-Vincent, 2023).

The above-mentioned documents are aimed at finding solutions to the problems of the formation of innovative potential at the macro-economic level and solving them. In particular, articles 23 and 24 of the Law «On Innovative Activities» provide general instructions on the organization of innovative activities. However, at the level of the enterprise's economy, each manager should be able to create a program of organizational changes, and a mechanism for its implementation, and analyze and evaluate the achieved results based on internal capabilities. According to many experts, the constant driving force behind innovation is increased competition.

To adapt to the competitive environment and increase the possibility of profit, the managers of the enterprise are required to constantly improve the organizational structure, create competitive advantages in a constantly changing environment and improve them. However, implementing the above-mentioned changes is not an easy task, and most managers suffer from a lack of experience and knowledge in this regard. Below, we will dwell on the structural changes and development mechanisms that should be implemented to organize innovative activities in the enterprises of our country, as well as the methods of analyzing the results.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Many scientists in the countries of the world have defined the concepts of innovation and innovative activity. According to Y. Schumpeter, «innovation is the main force that determines the future of the economy. (Schumpeter, 1947). However, Y. Schumpeter did not take into account that the time factor can play a role in the entry of an innovative new product into the market, that is, the fact that the product of the company that entered the market first attracts the attention of the consumer was neglected. P.F. Drucker expressed the opinion that innovation is a unique tool used by entrepreneurs in the fight against the competition, and it is in the form of various opportunities for business (Drucker, 2009). Drucker's point is interesting and worth noting. Because as the market develops, new opportunities will open up. The use of these opportunities depends on the ability and behavior of each entrepreneur. According to experts of the Organization for Economic Development and Cooperation (OECD), innovation is the main mechanism of economic growth (OECD, 2007). According to Damanpour's conclusion, the long-term success of the enterprise is the creation of sustainable innovation potential (Damanpour, 1991).

Sh. A. Karaboev and N. M. Babaeva categorized the definitions given by foreign scientists to the term «innovation» and evaluated the measures taken to develop innovative activities in our country. They concluded that it is necessary

to understand the sum of all labor processes related to the creation of inventions and their commercialization as a result of innovative activity (Koraboev Sh.A., Babaeva N.M., 2017). The definition given by these authors is very correct because to develop innovative activity, specialists and employees work together in different parts of the enterprise, and its result is noticeable in the increase of competitiveness and the increase of the enterprise's income. Shokirova G.Sh analyzed the work being carried out to increase innovative activity in our republic and made suggestions for further revitalization. In particular, the author believes that innovation is a constantly growing process, the radical improvement of the production process depends on fundamental scientific research, and the government should conduct a policy on the effective development of economic sectors. He also expressed the opinion that innovative potential is expressed in the establishment of new production enterprises, stimulation of existing ones, and creation of new types of products, and for this, it is necessary to develop measures to improve the management system, launch the production of new types of products, and encourage employees who create new technologies. concluded (Shokirova, 2018). In her article, Shokirova pointed out three important aspects of the development of innovative activities in enterprises: improving the management system, organizing the creation of new products, and encouraging employees who create new technologies. Although this conclusion is very appropriate, the measures for its implementation and the issues of creating a permanent working mechanism remain open. This means that it is necessary to comprehensively consider the issues of the formation of innovative potential.

Research methodology. Innovation research has three important features: experimental observation of innovation processes and systems, critical analysis of innovation theory, and decision-making based on innovation. One of these characteristics is the level of creation of innovations and their implementation. It is very important to compare how effectively the level of innovation affects the activity of manufacturing enterprises. Because the level shows the few or many barriers to innovation at the enterprise level and allows us to imagine the level of serviceability of the product. The main goal is to determine how much innovation has contributed to the company's growth rate.

Analysis and results. Some factors are considered important in studying the effectiveness of the innovative activity of the enterprise. For example, Narcizo, Kanen, and Tammela indicated the following as dimensions that determine the effectiveness of innovative activities for the enterprise: organizational structure, leadership, organizational culture, strategy, knowledge management, and human resources (Narcizo, R.B., Canen, A.G. and Tammela, I., 2017). In the approach of these scientists, indicators describing the internal innovation potential of the enterprise are given. However, for each of the listed indicators, a separate efficiency calculation method is needed. In this case, efficiency is considered by comparing the results obtained with the resources spent. The second group of researchers focused on the efficiency of innovation processes. Gamal, Salah, and Elrayyes focused only on 5

dimensions: strategy, processes, organization, interaction, and learning (Gama, D., Salah, T. and Elrayyes, E.N., 2011). This approach complements the one presented above and focuses on building innovative capacity. The idea presented in this approach complements the one above. That is, Gamal, Salah, and Elrays approach show the processes of formation of innovative potential, while Narsiko, Kanen, and Tammela describe the form of innovative potential. From this, we can conclude that in the formation of innovative potential in enterprises, we should first pay attention to the organization of innovative processes, and then evaluate the formed potential.

Having studied the above-mentioned opinions and the scientific opinions and opinions of other scientists on this issue, we believe that it is necessary to implement the following «action program» consisting of 6 stages in the organization of innovative activities in the enterprises of our country:

1). It is necessary to improve the organizational structure in the enterprise, and it is necessary to form a laboratory engaged in innovative developments or a team engaged in conducting other types of research, testing the results, and putting them into practice;

2). The management of the enterprise should pay attention to the quality of human resources for the formation and development of innovative potential. It is necessary to introduce a mechanism for attracting talented specialists and effectively using their services;

3). The enterprise should have developed a long-term competitiveness improvement strategy, and it should contain a deep analysis of the current state of the enterprise and a plan in the form of a «road map» of the level expected to be achieved in the future;

4). The company's management and the team should jointly establish a «knowledge management» system and learn to use it effectively. As knowledge management provides an opportunity to create a basic competitive advantage for the enterprise, it should be focused on creating a foundation for market leadership through technology transfer and assimilation of modern know-how developments;

5). A culture of innovative development should be formed in the enterprise. The meaning of this is that the enterprise should not work only for projects that bring large profits but should become a creator of products and production technologies that will ensure the competitiveness of the enterprise at the national and global level in the long term. In this case, the suggestion or opinion of every employee of the enterprise should be taken into account and given serious attention. The contribution of workers to innovative activity should be encouraged accordingly;

6). In the enterprise, the spirit of leadership and initiative should be instilled in the employees. Each worker - employees and managers should consider it their duty to contribute to innovative activities and try to be an example to their colleagues and show themselves as enthusiastic employees who can follow them. The most important thing is that the top managers of the enterprise should feel responsible for the development of innovative activities and work tirelessly in this regard.

The results of the observations show that there is insufficient attention to 2 important features in the organization of innovative activities in the industrial enterprises located in our country. The first feature is that employees and managers of the enterprise have very weak attention to learning. If this deficiency is not eliminated, there will be no conditions for the formation of human capital in enterprises and its use for the future of the enterprise. The second feature is that the organization of innovative activities requires a proper understanding of the existence of interdependence and influence in the organizational structure of the enterprise. The importance of this is that there should be no obstacles in the enterprise for the development of innovative potential, the enterprise should be able to provide services for innovative products or services and technology, that is, to support it. Otherwise, the innovative developments created in the enterprise will remain at the research stage or will become «prey» of competing enterprises.

Conclusions and suggestions. Organization of innovative activity is very important for enterprises of our country today. A company that does not pay attention to this issue will not be able to achieve stable growth in the future and will not be able to maintain its position in the market. Therefore, enterprises should pay serious attention not only to economic efficiency but also to innovative efficiency in their activities. In this case, the practice of separately studying and evaluating 2 important elements of innovative efficiency should be introduced.

The first is to evaluate the organizational effectiveness of innovative activities. In this process, it will be necessary to study the activity of every department and structure related to innovative activities and to evaluate their activity, contribution, initiative, and leadership in creating innovative products and services or technologies. In this case, it is necessary to study the interrelationship between the departments of the enterprise and their influence on each other.

The second is that the enterprise should study the market potential of each new innovative product or service type, and technology, and evaluate its «market efficiency» by forecasting its impact on future profits. Today, many forecasting methods and models have been created. However, the management of the enterprise should focus on finding and studying the opportunities and invisible forces of the target market in the forecast. Then the company will not be mistaken in choosing products and services for the market, errors will be reduced to a minimum.

Enterprises that have learned to manage innovative knowledge in the long term and can effectively apply it in practice will become leading enterprises, and their market position will strengthen year by year. To effectively organize the management of innovative knowledge in the enterprise, it is necessary to constantly monitor the quality of human resources and, having determined the priority areas of scientific research, ensure that the creation of new innovative developments becomes a continuous process.

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